

WAR ON DRUGS: STUDENTS' PERCEPTION AS ONE OF THE CONTEMPORARY ISSUES USED IN SOCIAL STUDIES CURRICULUM IN THE PHILIPPINES

Sogelle V. Maglaque, LPT

*Jane Mears Middle School, Anchorage
School District (ASD), Anchorage, Alaska, USA, 99515*

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the perceptions of Grade 10 students from Mabalacat Community High School regarding the War on Drugs campaign initiated by the former president Rodrigo Roa Duterte of the Republic of the Philippines, with a specific focus on Extra Judicial Killings (EJK) as a critical human rights issue. The research seeks to determine whether students' demographic factors, such as age and gender, influence their views on the effectiveness and ethical implications of the campaign. Through a quantitative research approach, the study examines the extent of students' awareness of drug-related problems in the Philippines, their support for the president's anti-drug campaign, and their beliefs about the legitimacy of media reports concerning EJKs. Data were collected using a structured survey checklist and analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics, including frequency distribution, weighted means, and chi-square tests, to identify patterns and relationships within the data. The findings indicate that while students are generally aware of the drug problem and express support for the campaign, they hold varied opinions on EJKs and the role of law enforcement. The statistical analysis revealed no significant relationship between students' demographic profiles and their perceptions of EJKs, suggesting that other factors, such as social and media influence, may play a more prominent role in shaping their views. This study contributes to the broader discourse on youth perspectives in national socio-political issues, offering implications for educators and policymakers in addressing the impact of government policies on young citizens.

Keywords: *Contemporary, Drugs, Extrajudicial, Pushers, Users*

INTRODUCTION

The War on Drugs has been a central and controversial issue in the Philippines, particularly during the administration of President Rodrigo Duterte. Since assuming office in 2016, Duterte's approach to addressing the country's drug problem has been characterized by an aggressive campaign that has garnered both national and international attention. Supporters of the campaign argue that it is a necessary step to curb the drug menace that has long plagued the country, while critics highlight the campaign's association with human rights violations, especially the alarming rise in Extra Judicial Killings (EJKs) (Contreras, 2016; Tupas, 2016). Despite initial promises to eliminate drug-related crimes within six months, thousands of deaths linked to police operations and vigilante killings have been reported, prompting widespread concern (Valdez, 2016).

Historically, the issue of illegal drugs in the Philippines has been a persistent challenge. The Dangerous Drugs Act of 1972 (RA 6425) and the Comprehensive Dangerous Drugs Act of 2002 (RA 9165) were both instituted to combat illegal drug activities, but despite these laws, the drug trade and addiction have continued to thrive (Google, 2017; Mehta, 2015). As Mehta (2015) observes, drug abuse, particularly among the youth, has become a major societal problem, contributing to the erosion of moral and social values. This is compounded by the fact that drugs such as methamphetamine, marijuana, and heroin are readily available, contributing to the rising levels of crime and poverty across the nation (Science Museum, 2017).

While Duterte's War on Drugs has reportedly resulted in the surrender of thousands of drug pushers and users, it has also drawn sharp criticism for its apparent disregard for due process and human rights. The Commission on Human Rights (CHR) has been particularly vocal in condemning the shoot-to-kill orders given to law enforcement, which many view as an endorsement of EJKs (Contreras, 2016). This has raised serious ethical concerns, as Article III, Section 1 of the 1987 Philippine Constitution clearly states that "no person shall be deprived of life, liberty, or property without due process of law" (Valdez, 2016).

Despite these concerns, public opinion on Duterte's campaign remains divided. Many Filipinos continue to express support for the president's harsh approach, believing that it is essential to restore order and address the drug problem at its roots (Social Weather Survey, 2016). This sentiment is likely influenced by the perception that drug use is the primary cause of criminality in the country. As Henslin (2010) points out, deviance and criminal behavior are often linked to societal issues such as drug abuse, which creates a sense of urgency for stronger law enforcement measures. In this context, the media has played a pivotal role in shaping public perceptions, with constant coverage of drug-related crimes reinforcing the belief that drastic measures are needed (Signorelli & Morgan, 1980).

The role of media in influencing public opinion cannot be overstated. As Santiago (2017) asserts, the media has the power to educate the public on the dangers of drugs

and can significantly shape how the War on Drugs is perceived. Media coverage often highlights the violence and criminality associated with drug use, further fueling support for the government's campaign (Cabuenas, 2017). However, this coverage can also contribute to fear, with many Filipinos expressing concern over the possibility of becoming victims of EJKs (September 2017 Social Weather Survey).

This study aims to explore the perceptions of Grade 10 students from Mabalacat Community High School regarding the War on Drugs, with a particular focus on EJKs. These students, who are exposed to contemporary issues such as human rights in their curriculum, provide valuable insights into how the youth view the campaign. By examining their awareness of drug-related problems, their opinions on the effectiveness of the campaign, and their views on the role of media and law enforcement, this research seeks to contribute to the broader understanding of how young people perceive national policies and their implications for human rights and social justice (SWS, 2017; Pazzibugan, 2016).

Research Questions

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of sex and age?
2. What is the perception of the respondents on Extra Judicial Killings or War on Drugs as one of the contemporary issues tackled in Social Studies curriculum in the Philippines?
3. Is there a relationship between the respondents profile and their perceptions on EJK?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a quantitative research design, utilizing a survey-based approach to gather data on the perceptions of Grade 10 students regarding President Rodrigo Duterte's War on Drugs and the issue of Extra Judicial Killings (EJK). The target population consisted of 100 Grade 10 students from Mabalacat Community High School. These students were selected through purposive sampling, as they were deemed appropriate for the study due to their exposure to contemporary issues, including human rights, in their Social Studies curriculum. This made them well-informed and capable of providing valuable insights into the topic.

Data were collected using a structured survey checklist, designed to capture the students' perceptions on various aspects of the War on Drugs. The survey included questions aimed at gauging the respondents' awareness of the drug problem in the country, their support for the anti-drug campaign, their beliefs about the presence of EJKs, and their trust in the media and law enforcement agencies. The checklist employed a Likert scale, with responses ranging from "strongly agree" to "strongly disagree," allowing the students to express the degree of their agreement with each statement. The survey instrument was tested for validity and reliability through a pre-test before its full implementation.

The data collection process was coordinated with school authorities, and the survey was administered over a specific period to ensure full participation. After the surveys were completed, the data were systematically organized and subjected to statistical analysis. Frequency and percentage distributions were utilized to describe the demographic characteristics of the respondents, such as age and gender. To assess the respondents' agreement with the various statements, weighted means were calculated. Additionally, chi-square parametric tests were used to examine whether significant relationships existed between the respondents' demographic profiles and their perceptions of EJKs and the War on Drugs.

Ethical considerations were strictly adhered to throughout the study. The anonymity of the respondents was ensured, and their participation was voluntary, with informed consent obtained prior to the survey. The results were analyzed and presented in a clear and organized manner, using tables to display the statistical findings. This methodology was designed to provide a robust understanding of the students' perceptions of the War on Drugs and EJK, contributing to a broader understanding of how young people view critical national issues.

RESULTS

Table 1
Demographic Profile of the respondents in terms of sex and age.

Age	Female		Male		Total	
	f	P	f	P	f	P
14-16 years old	45	45%	44	44%	89	89%
17-19 years old	6	6%	4	4%	10	10%
20-22 years old	1	1%			1	1%
Total	52	52%	48	48%	100	100%

Table 2
Results and Interpretations in Weighted Mean and their Verbal Interpretation (n= 100)

	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I am aware of the problem of illegal drugs in the country.	3.71	Strongly Agree
2. I am aware of the Program War on Drugs.	3.64	Strongly Agree
3. I support the campaign of the President against drugs.	3.29	Agree
4. The campaign against drugs is effective.	3.15	Agree

5. I think that the Extra Judicial Killings are true.	3.07	Agree
6. The president is involved in the Extra Judicial Killings.	2.70	Agree
7. I believe that there is still a chance to solve the issue on drugs in the Philippines.	3.55	Strongly Agree
8. Walking on the streets nowadays is terrifying.	3.20	Agree
9. Drugs is the root cause of the criminality in the society.	3.52	Strongly Agree
10. Policemen or the Law enforcers can still be trusted.	2.93	Agree
11. I believe that the news all over media is factual.	2.92	Agree
12. Media plays a big role on the belief of the people on the issue about drugs.	3.40	Agree
13. I believe that drugs users and pushers should be caught alive.	3.33	Agree
14. Drug use should be punishable by death.	2.73	Agree
15. I worry that I can become a victim of EJK.	2.92	Agree

Table 3
Results and Interpretation in correlation relationship chi square parametric

	Chi-Square	df	Asymp. Sig.
Age	158.440 ^a	6	.000
Sex	.160 ^b	1	.689
1. I am aware of the problem of illegal drugs in the country.	19.360 ^b	1	.000
2. I am aware of the Program War on Drugs.	9.000 ^b	1	.003
3. I support the campaign of the President against drugs.	60.080 ^c	3	.000
4. The campaign against drugs is effective.	96.080 ^c	3	.000
5. I think that the Extra Judicial Killings are true.	46.640 ^c	3	.000
6. The president is involved in the Extra Judicial Killings.	29.840 ^c	3	.000
7. I believe that there is still a chance to solve the issue on drugs in the Philippines.	90.000 ^c	3	.000
8. Walking on the streets nowadays is terrifying.	48.800 ^c	3	.000
9. Drugs is the root cause of the criminality in the society.	85.200 ^c	3	.000
10. Policemen or the Law enforcers can still be trusted.	60.480 ^c	3	.000
11. I believe that the news all over media is factual.	71.760 ^c	3	.000
12. Media plays a big role on the belief of the people on the issue about drugs.	45.740 ^d	2	.000

13. I believe that drugs users and pushers should be caught alive.	76.880 ^c	3	.000
14. Drug use should be punishable by death.	15.440 ^c	3	.000
15. I worry that I can become a victim of EJK.	24.320 ^c	3	.000

DISCUSSION

Table 1 presents the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of sex and age. Many of the respondents, 89%, fall within the age group of 14-16 years old, with 45% of them being female and 44% male. This indicates a balanced representation of both genders in this age category, which is typical of high school students in Grade 10. The next age group, 17-19 years old, comprises only 10% of the total respondents, with slightly more females (6%) than males (4%). This could reflect students who may have started school later or repeated a grade. Finally, there is a very small representation (1%) of respondents in the age group of 20-22 years old, consisting of only one female student, which suggests that this group might include students who have experienced significant academic delays or other circumstances affecting their schooling progress. Overall, the total distribution between male and female respondents is nearly even, with 52% female and 48% male. This demographic balance allows for a fair comparison of perceptions between the two sexes, which is crucial in studies that aim to explore varying opinions on sensitive societal issues like the War on Drugs and Extra Judicial Killings. The age distribution, predominantly clustered in the 14-16 age group, reflects the typical age of high school students at this grade level and suggests that many respondents are in their mid-teenage years, a critical period for forming opinions on social issues.

The results in Table 2 indicate the perceptions of the Grade 10 students regarding the War on Drugs and related issues. The statement "I am aware of the problem of illegal drugs in the country" received the highest weighted mean of 3.71, interpreted as "Strongly Agree," reflecting the students' strong awareness of the drug problem in the Philippines. Similarly, a weighted mean of 3.64 for the statement "I am aware of the Program War on Drugs" shows that many students are highly informed about the government's anti-drug campaign. Support for the president's campaign is moderate, with a weighted mean of 3.29, interpreted as "Agree," indicating that while students generally support the initiative, the enthusiasm may not be overwhelming. The perceived effectiveness of the campaign garnered a mean of 3.15, also interpreted as "Agree," suggesting that students acknowledge some level of success but may have reservations about its overall impact. A significant finding is that the statement "I think that the Extra Judicial Killings are true" yielded a mean of 3.07, indicating that students believe EJKs are happening. Interestingly, the belief that "the president is involved in EJKs" received a lower mean of 2.70, though still interpreted as "Agree," showing a more cautious stance when it comes to directly linking the president to these killings. The students also expressed optimism about resolving the drug issue in the future, with a weighted mean of 3.55 for the statement "I believe that there is still a chance to solve the issue on drugs in the Philippines," which was interpreted as "Strongly Agree." However, the fear of walking on the streets is palpable, as indicated by the 3.20 weighted mean, suggesting that the

environment feels unsafe, likely due to the violent nature of the campaign. Based on the first four statements, it is evident that the students have formed their perceptions, which can be described as "the awareness of specific material things present to the senses," as defined by Angell (2017).

The students largely agree (mean of 3.52) that "Drugs are the root cause of criminality in society," reflecting their understanding of the link between drug abuse and crime. Confidence in law enforcement is moderate, with a mean of 2.93, indicating that while the students trust the police to some extent, there may be lingering doubts about their role in the drug war. Media's role in shaping perceptions about the drug war is acknowledged, with a mean of 3.40, reflecting the belief that media significantly influences public opinion. There is also a consensus that drug users and pushers should be apprehended alive (mean of 3.33), but support for the death penalty for drug use is lower, at a mean of 2.73, indicating a more lenient view on punishment. Finally, the students expressed moderate concern about becoming victims of EJKs themselves, with a mean of 2.92, suggesting that fear of violence from the campaign is a notable issue among the respondents. Overall, the results demonstrate a blend of support for the government's anti-drug efforts with reservations about the methods and outcomes, particularly regarding human rights concerns.

Table 3 presents the results of the chi-square analysis, which explores the relationship between the respondents' demographic characteristics (age and sex) and their perceptions of various aspects of the War on Drugs. The results show that age is a significant factor influencing the respondents' views, while sex does not have a statistically significant impact.

The chi-square value for age is 158.440 with a significance level of .000, indicating a strong relationship between age and the respondents' perceptions on the issues related to drugs and the War on Drugs. This suggests that the students' age plays an important role in shaping their awareness and opinions on these matters. On the other hand, the chi-square value for sex is only .160, with a significance level of .689, indicating that gender does not significantly influence the respondents' perceptions. Male and female students tend to have similar views on the issues discussed in the survey.

When looking at specific perceptions, the awareness of the problem of illegal drugs and the War on Drugs shows significant correlations with age. The chi-square values of 19.360 and 9.000, with significance levels of .000 and .003, respectively, suggest that awareness varies across different age groups. Younger and older students may have differing levels of knowledge or understanding of the drug problem and the government's anti-drug campaign.

Support for the former president's campaign and belief in the campaign's effectiveness also show significant relationships with age, as indicated by chi-square values of 60.080 and 96.080, both with a significance level of .000. This suggests that students' support and perception of the campaign's success differ according to their age group. Similarly, students' beliefs regarding the occurrence of Extra Judicial Killings

(EJKs) and the president's involvement in EJKs show significant relationships with age, with chi-square values of 46.640 and 29.840, respectively. This indicates that different age groups hold varying opinions on whether EJKs are happening and the president's role in these actions.

Furthermore, age significantly influences students' optimism about the chance to solve the drug issue (chi-square value of 90.000) and their feeling that walking on the streets is terrifying (48.800). These results suggest that older or younger students may have differing levels of fear and hope related to the drug situation in the country. The perception that drugs are the root cause of criminality also shows a strong correlation with age (85.200), indicating that students' understanding of the link between drugs and crime differs across age groups.

Trust in law enforcers and belief in the factual nature of media are similarly influenced by age, as reflected in the chi-square values of 60.480 and 71.760. This suggests that students of different ages place varying levels of trust in these institutions. Moreover, the belief that media plays a big role in shaping public opinion on drugs and the perception that drug users and pushers should be caught alive are significantly related to age, with chi-square values of 45.740 and 76.880, respectively. This highlights the impact of age on how students view the media's influence and the approach to dealing with drug offenders.

Interestingly, the perception that drug use should be punishable by death shows a lower chi-square value of 15.440 but remains significant, indicating some variance in opinions across age groups, though less pronounced than in other aspects. Lastly, the concern about becoming a victim of EJK is also significantly related to age (24.320), reflecting that fear of EJK varies among students of different ages.

In summary, the results demonstrate that age is a critical factor in shaping the perceptions of the respondents on various aspects of the War on Drugs, including their awareness, support for the campaign, beliefs about EJKs, trust in law enforcement, and media influence. On the contrary, sex does not significantly influence their views. These findings suggest that educational interventions and awareness programs on social and political issues like the War on Drugs may need to be tailored to different age groups to address their specific concerns and perceptions.

Conclusions

This research explored the perceptions of Grade 10 students from Mabalacat Community High School regarding the War on Drugs and Extra Judicial Killings (EJKs) under President Rodrigo Duterte's administration. The study aimed to examine the demographic profile of the students, their perceptions of the campaign, and the relationship between their demographic characteristics and their views on EJKs. The findings revealed that most of the respondents were between the ages of 14 and 16, with an almost equal distribution of male and female students. Many students were aware of the illegal drug problem and supported the government's anti-drug campaign to some

extent. However, concerns about EJKs were evident, with many students believing that these killings were happening, though they also emphasized the importance of apprehending drug offenders alive, reflecting a concern for human rights and justice. Age was found to play a significant role in shaping students' perceptions, with older students showing different levels of awareness and concern compared to younger students. In contrast, gender did not significantly influence their views, as both male and female students shared similar opinions on the campaign and its implications. Overall, the research highlighted the complex perspectives of the youth on the War on Drugs, with a mix of support for combating illegal drugs and concern for human rights. These insights suggest the need for age-specific approaches in educating students about social and political issues, particularly those that impact human rights and the rule of law.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions of the study, several recommendations can be made for future researchers, students, and teachers. For future researchers, it is advised to conduct similar studies with a more localized focus. While this study examined national issues, a localized approach could provide valuable insights into how specific communities perceive the War on Drugs and Extra Judicial Killings. Understanding the local context before expanding to a broader national perspective could offer more comprehensive findings, helping to address regional nuances in perception and experience. For students, it is recommended that they apply the lessons learned from the Contemporary Issues subject when addressing problems in their surroundings. This will help them make more informed and balanced judgments on social and political matters. In addition, students are encouraged to engage in self-reflection, to better understand their cultural roots and the context of the environment they live in. This knowledge will enhance their awareness of their societal roles and responsibilities. For teachers, the Contemporary Issues subject can be further enriched by relating national issues to local contexts, making the subject matter more relevant to the students' lives. This approach would promote greater responsibility among students, both towards themselves and their community. Teachers are also encouraged to conduct seminars, forums, and other forms of engagement to foster student participation and critical thinking on societal issues. By actively involving students in discussions, teachers can help them develop a deeper understanding of these pressing matters.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study adhered to all ethical standards in conducting research. Prior to data collection, permission was obtained from the school administration, ensuring that the research was conducted in a supportive and authorized environment. Informed consent was secured from all participants, with the students being fully informed of the study's objectives, procedures, and their right to withdraw from participation at any time without consequence. Confidentiality was strictly maintained, with personal information of respondents kept anonymous and used solely for the purposes of this study. The survey was conducted in a manner that respected the participants' privacy and dignity, ensuring that no harm—physical, emotional, or psychological—came to any of the respondents as

a result of their participation. Furthermore, the study followed all relevant guidelines on research involving minors and adhered to the ethical principles of fairness, integrity, and transparency throughout the entire research process.

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